

FORMATION OF CREATIVE ACTIVITY OF PRIMARY SCHOOL
TEACHERS

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Abstract: *Primary education is one of the types of education that leaves a deep mark on the life of every child, and at this stage of education, pedagogues have a great responsibility. That is, the creative activity of elementary school teachers requires special study.*

Keywords: *Innovative pedagogy, education, upbringing, primary school, creativity.*

By the 21st century, this term began to be used in the field of education of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Especially in innovative pedagogy, which has started to form as a separate and young branch of pedagogy, we are constantly facing this term. Creativity is analyzed as a special indicator of innovative activity in the scientific works of many of our pedagogic scientists, such as J.G. Yoldoshev, R.A. Mavlanova. R.A. Mavlanova in her textbook entitled "Pedagogy, innovation, integration in primary education" specifically focused on the issues of creativity and its formation.¹. The content and essence of the concept of creativity are deeply analyzed in the manual. However, the scientific-theoretical, scientific-pedagogical aspects of the issue of creativity are recognized as a special object of scientific research.

In the concept of higher education of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the tasks of a specialist are defined as follows: "regardless of his activity, field, the specialist should have the ability to work in creative teams, training in the fields of management and marketing, the economic implementation of new technologies, social and cultural aspects should be clearly imagined". These thoughts are directly related to teachers. Because the fundamental changes that are taking place in our society, our penetration into market relations require the teacher to be aware not only of professional knowledge, but also of economic, legal, and technical knowledge, and to use such innovations in his pedagogical activities in a creative way to develop children in all

¹ R.A. Mavlanova's textbook "Pedagogy, innovation, integration in primary education"

aspects. creative) requires the ability to use. In this place, it is necessary to pay special attention to the primary school teacher.

Because primary school teachers are required to conduct their pedagogical activities taking into account the age, individual and psychological characteristics of primary school children. However, pedagogical and psychological mechanisms actively participate in the formation of a child's personality. That is, in the formation of a person, in addition to heredity, environment, upbringing, activities, many psychological features, situations and processes, such as the old experiences, concepts, mentality, interests and interests of a person occupy the main place. From this point of view, it can be said that various factors affecting the child's personality are definitely reflected in the human psyche, feelings, emotions, opinions.

The creativity of primary school teachers can be seen in knowing the psychological characteristics of children. Each science has its own object, field of study. For example, zoology studies the structure of animals, their living conditions, and astronomy studies celestial bodies and their properties. We know that psychology is a separate science and studies the psychic (spiritual) life, which is a separate field of reality. Because the word "Psychology" itself is derived from two Greek words: psyche (soul, soul) and logos (word, knowledge) and means "science of the soul".

But this meaning cannot reveal the true meaning of modern psychology. Because the modern science of psychology is the science of the psyche, its manifestation and development conditions (Goziev E). Psychology is a science that studies mental states, mental processes and their mechanisms (A.V.Petrovsky). Each of us has mental processes such as sensations, perception, attention, memory, imagination, speech, thinking, feeling, and agency².

Thinking plays an important role in the formation of cognitive activity of primary school students. Scientists who have studied the features of thinking have studied the child's thinking in the following three directions: - characteristic of thinking at a young age, - its development, - factors of formation of concepts. Although elementary school students learn a lot of scientific concepts in the course of their education, they mix and confuse various symptoms, signs, and characteristics learned in previous lessons. Because in them there is no integral connection between things and events and their signs.

²Psychology is a science that studies mental states, mental processes and their mechanisms (A.V.Petrovsky)

Relying on the psychological foundations specific to a certain period of child development, the quality of the skills and abilities acquired in them should be evaluated. The learning process can acquire a verbal and non-verbal character in relation to the level of development specific to each age of the student, while explaining to the students the essence of different situations and forms of knowledge. The important aspect of the period of primary education students is that the personal experience, language skills, and knowledge acquired by the child during the kindergarten age begin to be organized, he develops both intellectually, morally, and socially, and matures. begins to cry.

According to Jean Piaget, a psychologist from Geneva, sharp turns occur in the intellectual potential of a 6-7-year-old child. His memory is much better, falls into a certain system, order, now he remembers more things he wants. This period is sometimes used with the phrase "children of junior school age"³.

For a child studying in primary school, his personal achievements - in studies, in sports, and his reputation among children become very important. The most important thing is that this period is very sensitive and convenient for understanding the meaning of moral norms, mastering moral values and forming spiritual ideas. That is why respect for adults, respect for children, respect for parents, love for the Motherland, personal and social property are cultivated. The child begins to distinguish the difference between punishment and encouragement and tries to avoid being punished and not to be seen by many. Therefore, the good conditions created for the moral and spiritual education of the child in the family and in the place of education will have a significant effect in this period.

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³ Jean Piaget, a psychologist from Geneva

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